

A PHARMOCOINFORMATICS STRATEGY USING MOLECULAR DOCKING to INVESTIGATE PHYTOCOMPOUND as PARKINSON'S DISEASE INHIBITORS

Arshita Jindal^{#1}, and Neha Singh^{*2}

Department of Biotechnology, Meerut Institute of Engineering and Technology, Meerut 250005, India

ABSTRACT

Parkinson's disease (PD) is a syndrome of the central nervous system that originates tremors and hinders mobility, leading to neurodegenerative conditions. In this study, the inhibitory efficacy of phyto compound against Parkinson's disease is studied using molecular docking and their ADMET property against ligands. Based on their anti-Parkinson activity, 30 phyto compounds were chosen. Two different proteins were obtained for this study. For the study's analysis, a variety of approaches and tools were employed. The phyto compounds were found using PubChem and protein validation was accomplished using BIOVIA, PDBsum, PyRx, and SwissADME. ADME features of each molecule were investigated using SwissADME, and their toxicity was predicted using PROTOX 2, making them promising leads against Parkinson's disease. Based on the study, the ligands Besonprodil, bromocriptine, hesperidin, metixene, and piperine have the least binding affinities and might have an inhibiting influence on Parkinson's disease. These ligands have the finest ADMET properties.

Keywords: *Parkinson's disease, neurodegenerative, alpha-synuclein, DJ-1, ADMET, molecular docking, phyto compounds.*

I. Introduction

Neurodegenerative diseases are commonly identified as disorders with neuronal loss [1]. Many crippling, incurable disorders, like Parkinson's disease [2], are characterized by neurodegeneration. Neurodegenerative illnesses, which are age-dependent disorders, stance a serious hazard to human well-being due to the recent growth in the senior population [3]. Neurodegenerative diseases (NDs) are a group of chronic or likely genetic illnesses characterized by a shortage of neuronal subtypes over an extended period [4]. Parkinson's disease is the 2nd greatest prevalent neurodegenerative disorder, completely disturbing the quality of life, leading to dependency and early death in the diseased [5]. One of the most prevalent slow-progressing, chronic, age-related neurodegenerative disorders is PD, which is considered by forfeiture of dopaminergic (DA) neurons in the substantia nigra (SN) [6]. PD is a chronic, progressive disorder that causes motor, cognitive, emotional, and autonomic impairments [7]. The genes encoding a-synuclein, UCHL1, Parkin, DJ-1, and PINK1 are among five genetic alterations that are now linked to familial Parkinson's disease (PD) [8]. A crucial protein in the pathogenesis of PD is alpha-synuclein (alpha-Syn). The fact that alpha-synuclein aggregates quickly and

constitutes most Lewy bodies (LBs). DJ-1, initially identified as an oncogene that transforms when the ras gene is present, it was subsequently determined to be the reason for early-onset, autosomal declining Parkinson's disease [9], [10], [11]. Human DJ-1, a small (20 kDa) protein with 189 amino acid residues, is extensively expressed in over 22 human organs, such as the pancreas, kidney, skeletal muscle, liver, testis, and heart. It is a member of the enormous DJ-1/ThiJ/PfpI superfamily[12]. Computer-aided drug design can progress the capability for drug research and development [13]. CADD technologies used in drug design include quantitative structure-activity relationship (QSAR), molecular docking, and molecular dynamics simulation (MD) [14]. In contrast to docking, which is a static image, MD is utilized to detect the firmness of the bonds while analyzing the model and affinities of the interactions of enzymes and proteins with ligands and inhibitors [15], [16], [17].

II. Materials & Methods

A. Receptors and Ligand Selection

A total of 30 phytochemicals having inhibitory activity were selected for this investigation and are reported in Table 1. The PubChem database provides the 2D structural data for these ligands in SDF format, together with the PubChem CID, and canonical SMILES, [18]. These ligands were converted to the .pdb format using the open babel application [19].

B. Protein retrieval and Purification

The RCSB PDB [20] was used to resolve the alpha-synuclein with PDB id-6CT7 [21] and human DJ-1 with PDB id-2J7U [22] proteins, respectively, using the 2.50 and 1.90 resolution by the X-RAY diffraction method. Homology modelling was done using SWISS-MODEL [23] and protein structure stayed fined via removing ligand groups, heteroatoms, and water molecules from the protein structure using BIOVIA discovery Studio tool. The structure was then stored in files with the .PDB extension after it was cleaned up.

C. Validation of the Protein Structure

The Ramachandran plot provides a 2-D graphic depiction of all conceivable protein structures in terms of torsion angles (ϕ) and (ψ). The alphaL-region, alpha region, and beta region are the 3 main "acceptable" sections [24]. To construct the favourable region, the PDB sum generating process was performed to both pure proteins. The PDBsum generator was employed to generate the Ramachandran plot for the protein. The PDBsum generating homepage was launched, and the purified structure was placed in the appropriate spot before being uploaded.

D. Molecular Docking

PyRx is a molecular docking method used to simulate an interface between a slight particle and a protein at the atomic level [25]. It is compatible with Python programming language and is used to compare libraries of compounds against potential therapeutic targets. Flavonoids were added to pyrx as a ligand, and purified protein was involved as a macromolecule. The ligands were then converted to the .pdbqt format. Alpha-grid synuclein's and Human DJ-1's grid were used to evaluate nine different docking conformations to determine which had the highest binding score based on binding affinity. The optimal docking conformation was determined to be binding affinity equivalent to zero RMSD values. The top four conformities with the lowermost binding

affinities were elected to represent the optimum binding complex for each target protein. Docked ligand structures were obtained as .pdb files, and the interaction was shown using BIOVIA Discovery Studio. We examined the two- and three-dimensional interaction models. The best hit compound with 6CT7 underwent site-specific docking with the grid center coordinates of X:6.9274 Y:5.2827 Z:10.7449.

E. Physiochemical Studies

Therapeutic failure is mostly caused by a deficiency of effectiveness and safety, which indicates that chemical properties like ADMET—metabolism, absorption, excretion, distribution, and toxicity—should be examined by each step of drug research and development [26]. The ADMETlab 2.0 [27] uses canonical SMILES of the ligands using data from PubChem to analyze the ADME properties. The categorization of the prediction scheme into different categories of toxicity, such as hepatotoxicity and toxicological endpoints is a distinctive aspect of the ProTox-II [28]. By including canonical smiles from PubChem, toxicity is evaluated. Boiled egg is the physical space for passive diffusion across both physiological barriers.

F. Simulation

Dynamic simulations were employed in this work to keep track of a compound's stability. The compound was simulated using the GROMOS96 54a7 force field [29], and 0.15 M salt concentration was kept in accordance with the proportions of the box and amount of water molecules. System was remained simulated with a 2fs step size after being equilibrated at 310 K and 1 bar of pressure. A Berendsen thermostat was utilised to constantly heat the system at the NVT collective, and the Parinello-Rahman barostat procedure was applied for NPT. Protein was given a cubic form and size, 10A and 122312 water molecules, as well as NA + and Cl -, to improve stability and interactions.

III. Result

A. Selection of phytocompounds

The topmost five ligands that display the finest binding affinity for both proteins were selected based on the docking data from the PyRx. The 2D structural architecture of the ligands is shown in Fig. 1. Marvin-Chemaxon, the free sketching application was used to make these diagrams. Homology modeling depicts the following results for protein 6CT7, model was created in which model 1, which shows QMEANDisco value of 0.84 ± 0.06 with a 100% sequence likeness, has been chosen for further analysis. 8 templates and 1 model were generated from the protein 1J42 model 1, which shows QMEANDisco value of 0.90 ± 0.06 with a 100% sequence likeness, has been chosen for analysis.

TABLE 1

LIST OF LIGANDS

Phytochemical	Pubchem CID	Canonical Smile
Benserazide	2327	<chem>C1=CC(=C(C(=C1)NNC(=O)C(CO)N)O)O</chem>
Benztropine	1201549	<chem>CN1C2CCC1CC(C2)OC(C3=CC=CC=C3)C4=CC=CC=C4</chem>
Berberine	2353	<chem>COC1=C(C2=C[N+]3=C(C=C2C=C1)C4=CC5=C(C=C4CC3)OC5)OC</chem>
Besonprodil	156328	<chem>C1CN(CCC1CC2=CC=C(C=C2)F)CCS(=O)C3=CC4=C(C=C3)NC(=O)O4</chem>
Biperiden	2381	<chem>C1CCN(CC1)CCC(C2CC3CC2C=C3)(C4=CC=CC=C4)O</chem>
Bromocriptine	31101	<chem>CC(C)CC1C(=O)N2CCCC2C3(N1C(=O)C(O3)(C(C)C)NC(=O)C4CN(C5CC6=C(NC7=CC=CC(=C67)C5=C4)Br)C)O</chem>
Cabergoline	54746	<chem>CCNC(=O)N(CCCN(C)C)C(=O)C1CC2C(C3=CNC4=CC=CC2=C34)N(C1)CC=C</chem>
Carbidopa	34359	<chem>CC(CC1=CC(=C(C=C1)O)O)(C(=O)O)NN</chem>
Coumarin	323	<chem>C1=CC=C2C(=C1)C=CC(=O)O2</chem>
Curcumin	969516	<chem>COC1=C(C=CC(=C1)C=CC(=O)CC(=O)C=CC2=CC(=C(C=C2)O)OC)O</chem>
Ethybenzotropine	20055089	<chem>CCN1C2CCC1CC(C2)OC(C3=CC=CC=C3)C4=CC=CC=C4</chem>
Ferulic Acid	445858	<chem>COC1=C(C=CC(=C1)C=CC(=O)O)O</chem>
Gallic Acid	370	<chem>C1=C(C=C(C(=C1O)O)O)C(=O)O</chem>
Ginkgolides	11973122	<chem>CC1C(=O)OC2C1(C34C(=O)OC5C3(C2O)C6(C(C5)C(C)(C)C)C(C(=O)OC6O4)O)O</chem>
Halo	29976098	<chem>CC12CCC3C(C1CCC2(C)O)CCC4=C(C(C=CC34C)O)Cl</chem>
Hesperidin	10621	<chem>CC1C(C(C(C(O1)O)CC2C(C(C(C(O2)OC3=CC(=C4C(=O)CC(OC4=C3)C5=CC(=C(C=C5)OC)O)O)O)O)O)O)O</chem>
Levodopa	6047	<chem>C1=CC(=C(C=C1)CC(C(=O)O)N)O)O</chem>
Metixene	4167	<chem>CN1CCCC(C1)CC2C3=CC=CC=C3C4=CC=CC=C24</chem>
Pergolide	47811	<chem>CCCN1CC(CC2C1CC3=CNC4=CC=CC2=C34)CSC</chem>
Piperine	638024	<chem>C1CCN(CC1)C(=O)C=CC=CC2=CC3=C(C=C2)OCO3</chem>
Profenamine	3290	<chem>CCN(CC)C(C)CN1C2=CC=CC=C2SC3=CC=CC=C31</chem>
Punicic Acid	5281126	<chem>CCCCC=CC=CC=CCCCCCCCC(=O)O</chem>
Quercetin	5280343	<chem>C1=CC(=C(C=C1)C2=C(C(=O)C3=C(C=C(C=C3O2)O)O)O)O)O</chem>
Rasagline	3052776	<chem>C#CCNC1CCC2=CC=CC=C12</chem>
Retinoic Acid	444795	<chem>CC1=C(C(CCC1)(C)C)C=CC(=CC=CC(=CC(=O)O)C)C</chem>
Rosmarinic Acid	5281792	<chem>C1=CC(=C(C=C1)CC(C(=O)O)OC(=O)C=CC2=CC(=C(C=C2)O)O)O)O</chem>
Rotigotine	59227	<chem>CCCN(CCC1=CC=CS1)C2CCC3=C(C2)C=CC=C3O</chem>
Selegiline	26757	<chem>CC(CC1=CC=CC=C1)N(C)CC#C</chem>
Thymoquinone	10281	<chem>CC1=CC(=O)C(=CC1=O)C(C)C</chem>
Vipadenant	21874557	<chem>CC1=C(C=CC(=C1)CN2C3=NC(=NC(=C3N=N2)C4=CC=CO4)N)N</chem>

Fig. 1 2D structure of the selected ligands.

B. Protein Structure Analysis

Alpha-synuclein's purified 3D structure contains 92.2% of the protein's residues in the most favorable sections of the Ramachandran plot, followed by 6.7% of the residues in further permitted sections, 0.0% of the residues in generously allowed sections, and 1.1% of the residues in forbidden sections. 96.9% of the residues are found in the most desired areas of the purified 3D structure of DJ-1, 2.5% are found in further authorised sections, 0.0% are found in generously allowed sections, and 0.6% are found in banned sections. Fig. 2(a) depicts the Alpha-synuclein Ramachandran plot, whereas Fig. 2(b) depicts the DJ-1(b). PDBsum generator was used for the secondary structure prediction of proteins. The PDBsum result for the secondary structure prediction of alpha-synuclein include 7 beta alpha beta, 4 sheets, 4 beta bulges, 4 beta hairpins, 18 strands, 1 helix-helix interacts, 23 beta turns, 1 gamma turns, 3 helices, and 2 disulphides bonds. There are 3 beta alpha beta, 3 sheets, 2 beta hairpins, 11 strands, 11 helices, 1 beta bulge, 8 helix-helix interact, and 10 beta turns amid the PDBsum results for the protein secondary structure prediction of DJ-1. Alpha-synuclein has 212 total residues in its structure, while DJ-1 has 189 residues. Fig. 3(a) depicts the secondary structure of Alpha-synuclein, while Fig. 3(b) depicts DJ-1 (b).

Fig. 2 Ramachandran plot of protein 2(a) signifies a-synuclein 2(b) signifies DJ-1.

Fig. 3 Secondary structure of the protein 3(a) signifies a-synuclein whereas 3(b) signifies DJ-1.

C. Visualization and Molecular Docking

Proteins were docked with 30 ligands in this study. The protein binding affinities of the ligands are shown in Table 2. The ligands with the best binding affinities and lowest RMSD were carefully chosen after docking. The binding affinity was assessed, RMSD/ub, and r/lb of ligands after they were docked with the targeted proteins. 5

ligands were preferred for further investigation. These ligands are Besonprodil, bromocriptine, hesperidin, metixene, and piperine founded on their lowermost binding affinity.

TABLE 2
LIGAND BINDING ENERGY WITH ALPHA-SYNUCLEIN AND DJ-1 PROTEINS

Ligands	6CT7	1J42
Besonprodil	-7.3	-7
Bromocriptine	-8.1	-8.1
Hesperidin	-7.4	-7.9
Metixene	-7.2	-7
Piperine	-7	-7.1

Based on these docking results, besonprodil was chosen for site-specific docking with the pdb id -6CT7. The result of docking is shown in the table 3.

TABLE 3
BINDING ENERGY OF THE LIGAND WITH THE PROTEIN ALPHA-SYNUCLEIN

Ligand	6CT7
Besonprodil	-7.5

Using Dassault Systems BIOVIA Discovery Studio Visualizer, the elected ligand and protein were visualized, 2-D and 3-D models were obtained.

Fig. 4 2D interactions of Besonprodil interacting with protein alpha-synuclein.

Fig. 6 Boiled Egg image of ligand. Lipophilicity (WLOGP) and polarity (tPSA) computations were performed on gastrointestinal absorption and brain penetration datasets that had been cleansed, neutralised, standardised, and transformed into SMILE notation.

E. Simulation

In order to determine the RMSD and root mean square fluctuation, besonprodil was carefully chosen for molecular dynamics study in contrast to (PDB ID: 6CT7). (RMSF). Utilizing the GPU-enabled GROMACS 2019.4 program, the considered molecular docking findings remain imperilled to molecular dynamics simulation. With the Prodrug server, the Ligand topology was constructed before the default parameters were inserted [30]. System placed in cubic box, prepared for 1500 steps using GROMACS steepest descent method. The dynamic structure was sustained at a typical 0.15 M salt concentration by inserting Na⁺ and Cl⁻ counter ions. The segment was imperilled to an ultimate run for NPT equilibration lasting 50 ns, and the RMSF and RMSD graphs were created utilizing trajectory files and standard parameters. The makers of GROMACS provided the rms, rmsf, gyrate, and sasa functions, which are also accessible on their official website. GROMACS 2019.4 was used. Evaluation of protein-ligand interactions for the purpose of developing new medications is the main objective of molecular dynamics investigations. The positional separation of one or more atoms is defined by the average deviation found among the equivalent atoms of the proteins in the RMSD plot (Fig. 7A), whereas the RMSF plot shows, amount of positional variation of actual atom over period (Fig. 7B). The radius of gyration controls how structure compresses (Fig. 7C). The protein remained compressed throughout the simulation period, as seen in Fig. 7C, with no discernible quick decreases or peaks, proving that there were no significant structural transition simulations. The SASA plots display all the protein's surface that is accessible by the ligand molecule (Fig. 7D). The action of a medication is determined by the ligand's affinity for the protein's active or allosteric site. Additionally, Figure 7E implies protein-ligand interactions remain commonly stabilised by hydrogen bonds.

Fig. 7 Plots to show how well the best lead chemical reacts with the target protein. (A) RMSD (B) RMSF (C) Radius of gyration (D) SASA (E) H-bond interaction plot.

IV. DISCUSSION

Parkinson's illness has been known for more than 200 years[30]. Understanding the genetic factors influencing Parkinson's disease risk, onset, and progression is critical for developing treatments that could slow or halt disease progression [31]. DJ-1 protein has several distinct methods for protecting dopaminergic neurons from neurodegeneration in Parkinson's disease [32]. In these nations, the number of people over the age of 50 with Parkinson's disease remained between 4.1 and 4.6 million in 2005, and it is anticipated to grow between 8.7 and 9.3 million by 2030 [33]. The age-adjusted impermanence rate after Parkinson's disease amplified from 5.4 per 100,000 populace in 1999 to 8.8 per 100,000 populace in 2019, through an average yearly per hundred change of 2.4%. PD mortality amplified dramatically athwart all age ranges, both genders, numerous racial/ethnic groupings, and varied urban-rural organizations from 1999 to 2019 [34]. For the past 20 years, α -synuclein pathology has been recognised as a critical condition of Parkinson's disease and associated α -synucleinopathies [35].

Levodopa is the maximum effective symptomatic therapy for Parkinson's disease (PD) and serves as the gold standard against which other medicines must be measured [36]. LD maintains the gilt standard for suggestive efficiency in the pharmacological treatment of PD after more than 40 years of clinical usage [37]. Long-term therapy with LD, on the other hand, is sometimes worsened through the emergence of several forms of motor response fluctuations throughout the day, along with drug-induced dyskinesia, a condition characterised thru unpredictable involuntary movements [38]. Besonprodil (CI-1041) is an NMDA antagonist that is specific for the NR2B subunit [39]. It is being researched as a PD supplement therapy, and it has been proven in animals to

be beneficial in reducing the dyskinesias accompanied with continuing treatment with levodopa and similar treatments [40].

Recently, the in-silico drug design method has become more and more prevalent. It analyses the consequences of pharmacophore screening, molecular docking, post docking interaction analysis, molecular dynamic simulation (MDS), and calculation of noble drug compounds counter to a variety of diseases in a computer-simulated environment [41]. The purpose of this method is to find interesting compounds that may be further evaluated and optimised in the laboratory by utilizing computational tools and techniques to examine the characteristics and relations of possible therapeutic applicants in a simulated environment [42]. Researchers can forecast drug candidates binding affinity and discernment, analyze drug-protein complex stability and conformational dynamics, and predict drug candidates in contradiction of exact target proteins or disease pathways [43]. It is possible to forecast how a number of molecules are going to interact if they possess the least binding affinity and the highest compositional confirmation using a process called molecular docking[44].

Based on their pharmacological action, 30 flavonoids were preferred for this research. The targeted protein with the pdb id 6CT7 and 1J42 has the lowest binding affinity with the ligands Besonprodil, bromocriptine, hesperidin, metixene, and piperine. These ligands were elected for additional visualisation. These ligands had binding affinities of -7.3, -8.1, -7.4, -7.2, and -7 with alpha-synuclein and -7, -8.1, -7.9, -7, and -7.1 with dJ-1 respectively. The BIOVIA discovery studio was used to visualize its 2-D structure. The most common amino acids present in the 2-D structure were discovered to be ASN:94, HIS:33, and ILE:95.

Additional in-silico research was performed on the top 5 substances to look at their ADMET and drug-likeness properties. The finest features, as determined by the physiochemical properties of these drugs, are exhibited by besonprodil, which has logs = -4.066 and nHA = 5 hydrogen bond acceptors, nHD = 1 hydrogen bond donor, nRot = 6 rotatable bonds, nHet = 7 heteroatoms and nRing = 4 rings. Lipinski's criteria for choosing, molecular weight ranges from 150 to 500 g/mol, and there are 1 H bond giver and 5 H bond acceptors. The Lipinski filtration research shows that all the phytochemicals in the chart have possible pharmacological effects.

Due to its 3.53 synthetic ease, besonprodil can also be produced in a dry environment. Additionally, it has an adequate number of sp³ hybridised carbons in contrast to other ligands. Additionally, meanwhile the drug must pass the gut barrier beforehand reaching the systemic bloodstream, intestinal absorption in humans is essential for an oral medication to appear effective. The permeability of Caco-2 cells is used as a sign of a suitable potential medication molecule. All four ligands were expected to pass caco-2 and reach the mammalian gut. Given this, besonprodil is more likely to be absorbed into the gut barrier.

Using Papp values of MDCK cell lines, the efficacy of chemical absorption into the body and the encouragement of the blood-brain barrier are assessed, and all four chemicals exhibit minimal permeability. Besonprodil may be able to influence its target region in high to moderate amounts due to its potent capacity to bind to plasma proteins. Since all the substances are anticipated to penetrate the blood-brain barrier, they may all reach the CNS. Medication-induced liver injury has been the most common safety worry associated with medication recalls over the past 50 years. (DILI). The findings show that no chemical is toxic to liver cells and that humans can safely consume everyday amounts. While other ligands induce some level of toxicity, besonprodil fulfilled all the criteria for toxicity.

The molecular dynamics (MD) modelling analysis of protein ligand complex underneath Gromos 43a1 force field in water was conducted using the Gromacs 4.5.5 software, a high-end, high-performance research device developed for the investigation of protein dynamics by means of classical molecular dynamics theory [45][46]. A beginning structure for the ligand was created using the PRODRG server. Additionally, the findings of molecular docking and modelling demonstrate the ligand's strong affinity for the receptor.

V. CONCLUSION

Parkinson's disease is one of the fastest increasing neurological conditions in the world. The current worldwide effect of neurological illnesses is reflected in the most recent worldwide Burden of Diseases (GBD) study. The researchers found that neurological conditions are the second leading cause of death after heart disease, accounting for 9.0 million fatalities and 16.5% of all deaths worldwide. In the last 20 years, the amount of people with Parkinson's disease has more than doubled, most likely as a result of ageing and the disease's protracted course. It is alarming because PD cases are doubling every two years, and it is likely that it will take considerably longer than necessary to reach 12 million cases. The organic compounds polyphenols, alkaloids, tannins, carbohydrates, steroids, flavonoids, and terpenoids are all originate in curative plants. These chemicals might be castoff to find as well as create fresh anti-Parkinson's treatments. It has been demonstrated that the novel phytochemical besonprodil, which was docked against anti-diabetic receptors, is useful in treating people with Parkinson's disease. Therefore, a description of how anti-diabetic herbs and phytochemicals affect the pharmacokinetics of anti-diabetic drugs may be pertinent for enhancing the management of diabetes.

Disclosure Statement

There is no conflict of interest.

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